

DIFFICULTIES OF TEACHING ENGLISH FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

Jo'rayeva Muhayyo Abdujalilovna

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences
Faculty of History and Philology
Teacher of the Department of
Foreign Language and Literature

Abstract. This article is mainly concerned with the problems of teaching English as a foreign language to the young generation and some difficulties that arise in the learning process.

Key words: English language, methodology, skills, professional education, teacher, student, vocabulary

Introduction. One of the main indicators of the state development is the competitiveness of its educational system, science and technology. Thus, the role of language in the development of the nation, state, and society is explained as very important, necessary and urgent. Moreover, these concepts are directly related and interconnected concepts. As the nation, state, and society develop, its language and linguistics develop. Changes in the state and society are first of all reflected in the language, in particular, in its lexicon - the enlargement of the vocabulary.

As long as language is social in nature, progress in social life determines progress in language. And in turn, the development of language and linguistics affects the development of society and the state. At present, English is finally established as a language of world importance. The ability to know foreign languages is becoming one of the integral parts of professional education.

In modern society, It is crucial to follow modern tendencies of teaching and learning foreign languages. People learn such knowledge first at school, college, lyceum, and later at higher educational institutions, in training courses or independently by getting acquainted with the basic information sets that help to learn a foreign language.

Contemporary, knowledge of foreign languages is not only a sign of cultural development of a person, but also one of the important conditions for successful activity in various spheres of life. It can also be said that knowledge of foreign languages is becoming a vital necessity nowadays. It is also worth noting that today, when the flow of information is increasing not hourly, but minute by minute, knowledge and skills are the most important values of human life.

Today's fast-paced life shows that a person needs to use not only materials in his native language, but also foreign information in order to be aware of all the news of world experience in his field. In addition, the entry of modern information technologies into our lives - computer and Internet, means of communication also requires perfect learning of foreign languages.

Because in order to use such modern information technologies, it is necessary to have certain skills in international languages. Currently, conditions are being created for young people to work in cooperation with their peers in the most developed countries, and modern specialists with their colleagues through the Internet. By knowing a foreign language, it is possible to further increase the level of knowledge. For example, if you study Latin, you can learn the origin of many English words.

Learning a foreign language helps to further expand a person's knowledge base. Learning foreign languages, especially reading literature in its original form, is also the key to unlocking the undiscovered aspects of knowledge. The task of English language teachers is not only to teach students or to focus more on their English language skills, such as reading, writing, listening and speaking, but also to teach them English. It is also about helping and encouraging by providing enthusiasm, good attitude and great motivation.

Despite this, teachers today face a number of difficulties and obstacles in teaching English. These are the following:

1. Disrupted classroom environment. The environment is very important in teaching and learning English. A disturbing classroom environment distracts

students and negatively affects language learning. A suitable and comfortable environment is the main need for teaching English. If the environment is not suitable and comfortable for the students, it will destroy the English language learning process. In teaching English, mainly teachers face such an unfavorable environment.

2. Limited teaching resources. Teaching anything, not just English, depends on many resources. Teachers often face such problems. That is, teachers do not provide students with the necessary resources to learn English effectively. Without them, it will be very difficult to teach and learn the language. Resources include speakers, microphones, projectors, computer systems, and other types of digital devices. With these, teaching and learning will be more effective and interesting.

3. The number of students in the class. Having a large number of students in the classroom creates a lot of anxiety and stress for teachers. Because in order to teach a large number of students, teachers have to make more effort and hard work. Teachers need time to observe their students and teach them at their level. However, there is very little class time allocated for teaching this subject. This is a very difficult task for teachers to teach in a short time. Another notable problem that teachers face is that students are completely dependent on teachers.

They do not try to learn and speak themselves. Students always turn to teachers to help them learn and give them the right answers. They do not try to correct words and sentences when speaking English. In this problem, students have not learned the technical terms of using different tenses and words in English. Students' boredom and lack of interest in learning English is also a problem faced by teachers. Educating the current young generations and finding them highly competent is not only the teacher's duty, but also related to the family environment and the attention of the neighborhood.

Scientific studies and researches show that 80% of all the information that a person receives during his life before the age of 6 shows the importance of preschool education in the development of a child's personality. At the meeting held by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on August 16, 2017, in

order to determine the measures for 100% inclusion of 5-6-year-old children in preschool educational institutions, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan the decision "On organizing the activities of the Ministry of Education" was adopted. And in these institutions, it was decided to teach English from an early age. The reason is, as our ancestors used to say, "the knowledge acquired in youth is a pattern carved in stone."

This is not for nothing, as shown in this article, the earlier learning begins, it will lead to the elimination of some of the above-mentioned problems and difficulties, and the easier acquisition of language skills and competencies. It is. Especially if this knowledge, skills and abilities are absorbed through various games and educational activities, the child develops foreign languages as naturally as his mother tongue.

Educational games not only form knowledge, skills and abilities in a child, but at the same time, they ensure the child's healthy physical development, mentally refresh, strengthen self-confidence and have a great opportunity to form social relations with others. It gives mark. At the same time, the existing problems in language teaching that have been pointed out in this article, that is, the problems between teachers and young generations, can be eliminated based on the solutions mentioned.

In conclusion, the problems arising in the process of teaching a foreign language considered in the article lie in the lack of necessary educational resources, the fact that old teaching methods are still used in most educational institutions, and the educational environment is not good. It is possible to increase the level of students' mastery of the lessons and achieve the effectiveness of the lesson through the teaching methods presented above as a solution to these problems. At the same time, in any situation, a teacher should have the ability to think highly, observe problems, and solve problems in time.

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